

VIETNAM NATIONAL UNIVERSITY, HANOI
UNIVERSITY OF LANGUAGES AND INTERNATIONAL STUDIES
FACULTY OF POST-GRADUATE STUDIES

CAO VÂN ANH

THE INFLUENCES OF ELSA SPEAK ON ENGLISH SPEAKING
COMPETENCE OF 10TH GRADERS IN A SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

*(Ảnh hưởng của ELSA Speak đối với năng lực nói tiếng Anh của học sinh
lớp 10 ở một trường Trung học Phổ thông)*

M.A THESIS (Applied program)

Field: English Teaching Methodology

Code: 8140231.01

Hanoi - 2024

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Supervisor: Dr. Huỳnh Anh Tuấn

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DECLARATION

I certify that this minor thesis, submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Arts in English Language Teaching Methodology at the Faculty of Post-Graduate Studies, University of Languages and International Studies, Vietnam National University, Hanoi is the result of my work, and it was not previously submitted, in whole or in part, with any other application for a degree. Also, I have provided fully documented references to the work of others. The material in this thesis is entirely my own, except where stated otherwise by reference or acknowledgment.

Hanoi, 2024

Supervisor

Dr. Huỳnh Anh Tuấn

Cao Vân Anh

Date:.....

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to investigate the impacts of ELSA Speak, which is an educational application, on improving students' English speaking competence at a senior high school. This is action research, and the instruments utilized for data collection included two tests (pre-test and post-test) for students, a questionnaire, and a personal interview for each of them. The participants were 15 students in a class at a senior high school. The findings are expected to indicate that they all have favorable attitudes towards the use of ELSA Speak on a daily basis after 2 months of employing this application. Additionally, it is revealed that ELSA Speak can be a powerful tool to facilitate more rapid progress in the participants' confidence as well as their speaking competence. There are further pedagogical implications arising from these findings. This research is supposed to be of profound significance to both teachers and students in teaching and learning English language speaking skills.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

- AI: Artificial Intelligence
- ASR: Automatic Speech Recognition
- ELSA: English Language Speech Assistant
- CEFR: Common European Framework of References for Languages

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CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Rationale for the study

Learning English language involves four major skills, namely reading, listening, speaking, and writing. Additionally, speaking competence is one of the ultimate goals of learning English language for students of all levels. According to Brown and Yule (1983), speaking is the skill used to judge language learners in most real-world situations.

Notwithstanding, due to a dearth of communicative environment, it can be a challenge for students to learn English speaking skill, especial for those who are in rural areas.

In the past few years, ELSA Speak application has been employed as a tool to supplement students' pronunciation and other aspects regarding speaking skills. Developed based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology, this application uses Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) in order to analyze every single word pronounced by users and give them feedback on their performance. In general, ELSA Speak equips its users with a multitude of functions that are believed to help them speak English more comprehensively.

So far, the application of ELSA Speak by non-native speakers has been a topic of concern for various researchers. Some of them focused on the special features of ELSA Speak from students' perception while some put their effort to investigate the use of this mobile application in a certain classroom setting. However, there are fewer papers that are about the impacts of ELSA Speak on students' English speaking competence and their attitudes towards this application in the context of self-study at home. Based on the literature review along with the concrete teaching English situation at school, this study is conducted to bridge this gap.

As a teacher of English, the researcher does understand the obstacles of students while trying to sharpen their speaking skills without a native speaking environment. Moreover, the importance of speaking English fluently and understandably cannot be ignored. Therefore, the researcher decided to undertake this study with a view to finding a new way to supplement teaching speaking skills in Vietnamese schools.

1.2. Aim and objectives of the study

This research aims at exploring the influences of using ELSA Speak on improving students' speaking competence in a senior high school. This general aim can be accomplished by the following objectives:

- *To explore the impacts of ELSA Speak on students' speaking competence*
- *To investigate students' attitude towards the implementation of ELSA Speak in the context of self-study*

1.3. Research questions

In order to accomplish the aforementioned aims and objectives, the research is conducted to answer the following question:

- *What are the influences of ELSA Speak on improving students' English speaking competence in a senior high school?*
- *What are the students' attitudes towards the use of ELSA Speak in order to enhance their English speaking skills?*

1.4. Scope of the study

The participants of this study are fifteen 10th graders at a senior high school in Ninh Binh. The study involves the marked effects of ELSA Speak on students' speaking competence and students' perspectives on the implementation of ELSA Speak. Anything that is not related to these two considerations, therefore, would be beyond the scope.

1.5. Method of the study

From the aforementioned research question, there are three corresponding hypotheses:

- ELSA Speak exerts positive impacts on English language learners
- ELSA Speak has salutary influences on students' attitudes toward learning speaking skills
- ELSA Speak helps to improve students' English speaking competence

The study adopts action research to achieve its objectives. The research instruments are tests (pre-test and post-test), questionnaire, and semi-structured interview.

1.6. Significance of the study

The significance of the study includes the following parties:

For the teachers of English at this school: This research can be used to enhance the method of imparting English speaking abilities so that the teaching and learning process can be successful and produce a significant improvement in the speaking ability of the students.

For this school's students: Interactive exercises on the application can help students become more fluent speakers.

For the author: The study will enable the author to identify a crucial, previously unexplored area in the teaching and learning of English. The results could serve as a crucial starting point for more research.

In general, this research endeavors to contribute to the theoretical discourse surrounding language acquisition, particularly in the context of technology-mediated learning. By investigating the influences of Elsa Speak on the English speaking competence of 10th graders in a senior high school, this study aims to offer insights into the efficacy of language learning applications. By extending existing theories on language acquisition to

encompass contemporary educational tools such as Elsa Speak, this research seeks to deepen our understanding of the factors influencing second language acquisition among adolescent learners. Furthermore, findings from this study hold the potential to inform educational policies concerning the integration of technology in language learning curricula, thus bridging the gap between theoretical insights and practical applications in language education.

In addition to its theoretical contributions, this research holds practical significance for English language educators, students, and policymakers alike. By elucidating the impact of Elsa Speak on English speaking competence, this study offers practical guidance for teachers seeking to enhance their instructional methods through technology integration. Furthermore, insights gleaned from this research can empower students to take agency over their language learning journey by leveraging supplementary resources such as language learning apps. By addressing the challenges faced by high school students in speaking English fluently, this research provides actionable recommendations for educators to tailor their approaches and support individualized learning experiences. Ultimately, by bridging theory and practice, this research seeks to enrich language education pedagogy and facilitate more effective English language learning outcomes in high school settings.

1.7. Structure of the study

The thesis covers the following parts:

Chapter 1: Introduction gives readers a broad overview of the research, including the rationale for the study, its objectives, the research questions, the scope, the significance, the research methodology, and the structure of the study.

Chapter 2: Literature review discusses the key ideas in speaking ability, the science behind the mechanism of ELSA Speak in an effort to give

the subsequent chapters a theoretical foundation. An overview of similar papers is additionally provided.

Chapter 3: Methodology details the process used to gather the study's data, as well as the background information on the environment in which it was done. The justification for using action research, the tools used to gather data, and the study methodology are also discussed.

Chapter 4: Findings and Discussion sheds light on the information gathered from the tests, questionnaire, and interview. An assessment of the intervention's efficacy can be made based on the data analysis. This chapter is also to further explain the insights that resulted from the data analysis, and evaluate and discuss the relevance of the findings in respect to what was already known about the research problem being explored.

Chapter 5: Conclusion recapitulates the study's topics, offers advice for instructors, identifies its limitations, and makes some recommendations for future research.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

In an effort to provide a theoretical framework, this chapter examines the fundamental principles of speaking ability as well as the science behind the ELSA Speak system. An overview of similar papers is additionally provided.

2.1. Students' speaking competence

2.1.1. Definition of speaking

Speaking, which is one of the two crucial productive skills in language learning, has been defined differently by various researchers. Bygate (1987) regards it as a process of producing auditory signals, leading to varied verbal responses from listeners. In other words, it can be considered a systematic way of combining sounds to create meaningful utterances. Moreover, Burns and Joyce (1997) state that speaking is an interactive process that involves producing, receiving, and processing data to construct meaning.

According to Chaney (1998), speaking can be understood as making and sharing meaning by employing verbal and non-verbal symbols in dissimilar contexts. Furthermore, Eckard and Kearny (1981), Florez (1999), and Howarth (2001) do agree on the viewpoint that speaking is a two-way process which includes a concrete communication of ideas, emotions, and information.

Speaking is one of the two components of a lesson, according to Riddell (2003). Reading aloud or reading the answer to a grammar question is not speaking. Similarly, speaking is neither reading the answer to a reading/listening inquiry nor repeating it orally. In each of these instances, the objectives are unrelated to speaking. It could be a speaking activity intended to provide practice of a recently learned or reviewed language.

Brown (2004) describes speaking as an observable and immediately measurable productive skill. Speaking is the result of the creative building of

linguistic strings, with the speaker making decisions regarding vocabulary, structure, and discourse.

Thornburry (2007) proposes several aspects of diverse speaking events in order to characterize various speaking genres. Transactional functions are separate from interpersonal functions. The primary objective of the transactional function is to transmit information and facilitate the exchange of goods and services, whereas the interpersonal function is all about maintaining and fostering positive relationships between individuals.

Speaking, according to Spratt, Pulverness, and William (2011), is a productive ability similar to writing. It entails utilizing language to communicate with others. As people talk, they utilize various components of speech depending on the sort of speech they are engaged in. Thus, speaking is a complicated action.

All in all, from the above-mentioned definitions of speaking, the most suitable way to conceive the meaning of speaking throughout this study is an interactive process of forming utterances that convey information or emotions with a systematic way of combining sounds in a language.

Brown & Yule (2000) acknowledge that teaching speaking is to equip students with an ability to express themselves in a certain language under interactive circumstances such as exchanging greetings, thanks and apologies, and so on. As English is one of the universal languages that are internationally used, speaking English well can be the key to update the latest news and information in different fields (Joanna and Heather, 2003). Accordingly, learners with high English speaking competence not only arm themselves with a valuable skill and broad knowledge but also stand good chances of contributing to their home countries.

In short, teaching and learning English speaking skill is tremendously beneficial, especially in the era of globalization as today.

2.1.2. Components of speaking skills

There are five components of speaking abilities, according to Harris (1974): comprehension, grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, and fluency. These five elements closely resemble those of the CEFR speaking rubric. Particularly, Harris's perspective and the CEFR framework share the components of grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation. Rather than employing the term "discourse management", Harris referred to "fluency". In nature, however, these two components are identical. In the same vein, there are numerous parallels between the components of interactive communication in the CEFR and understanding in Harris's book. The author chose to utilize the speaking components of Harris since they are simpler and more transparent to comprehend and apply in the development of research instruments.

2.1.2.1. Pronunciation

Kline (2001) opines that pronunciation is the process through which language learners create clearer speech when speaking. This means that each student may communicate successfully if they have outstanding pronunciation and intonation, even if their vocabulary and grammar are restricted. So, one might argue that proper pronunciation enables pupils to articulate words effectively when speaking. According to Fraser (2008), pronunciation incorporates all characteristics of speech that contribute to a readily understood speech flow, including segmental articulation, rhythm, intonation and phrasing, gestures, body language, and eye contact.

2.1.2.2. Grammar

Eleni (2011) affirms that grammar is crucial to language acquisition. A student is considered to be proficient in a language when he or she is able to construct grammatically correct sentences in the target language and employ these forms appropriately according to context. This implies that understanding grammar is a prerequisite for effective language acquisition and a crucial

component of language instruction. The right application of a language's grammar is a description of the ways in which words can change their forms and be employed to build sentences in that language (Harmer, 2001). Furthermore, grammar is the study of how words join to make sentences, as described by Nelson (2001). In addition, grammar is a guideline that enables learners to combine accurate sentences in written and spoken dialogue.

2.1.2.3. Vocabulary

Vocabulary is the comprehension of word meanings (Rora, 2015). Without necessary vocabulary, students will be unable to employ the structure and grammatical functions they have acquired to communicate in a way that is intelligible. Vocabulary is the right use of diction. Additionally, language facilitates the verbal and written expression of ideas, emotions, and thoughts. Vocabulary is a fundamental aspect of language acquisition. Learners must understand words, their meanings, their spellings, and their pronunciations.

2.1.2.4. Fluency

Hughes (2002) defines fluency as the capacity to explain oneself in a comprehensible, rational, and flawless manner without hesitation; otherwise, the conversation would fail as listeners lose interest. To attain this objective, teachers should urge students to freely use their own language to communicate their own views and to avoid imitations of any type. One may argue that fluency is the ability to react coherently by connecting words and sentences effectively and pronouncing sounds clearly. The goal is for pupils to talk freely and eloquently. The instructor does not immediately correct the pupils' errors since doing so would disrupt the natural flow of dialogue.

2.1.2.5. Comprehension

Comprehension is defined as the ability to comprehend and process the main points of discourse in to develop interpretations of the meaning of sentences. Studying the comprehension of a second language is more difficult.

Participants must comprehend the nature of the study endeavor, even if the processes are hard and many. Lado (2005) defines speaking ability as the capacity to apply stress, intonation, grammatical norms, and vocabulary in regular conversation, in which comprehension is an indispensable element.

2.1.3. Types of speaking performance

Brown (2001) suggests that there are six types of classroom speaking performance, namely: Imitative, intensive, responsive, transactional, interpersonal, and extensive. The planning actions for participants in this research are closely based on Brown's theory aligned with practical features on ELSA Speak. In particular, those are described as follows:

**** Imitative***

This category consists of the capacity to rehearse pronunciation and concentrate on specific parts of language form. This is only a copy of a word, phrase, or sentence. The instructor incorporates drilling into the learning process so that students have the chance to listen to and verbally repeat certain terms.

**** Intensive***

This is the speaking performance of the students. Several phonological and grammatical parts of language are practiced. Typically, students are assigned activities in pair or group work, such as reading aloud, including reading paragraphs, discussions with partners, reading information from charts, etc.

**** Responsive***

Performance that is responsive involves interaction and test comprehension. Occasionally, it involves relatively brief interactions, conventional greetings and small talk, and straightforward requests and

remarks. This consists of brief responses to questions or remarks posed by the teacher. These responses are often adequate and relevant.

** Transactional (dialogue)*

It is conducted with the goal of sharing or transmitting certain information. As an example, consider conversational pair work.

** Interpersonal (dialogue)*

It is performed with the intention of preserving social bonds. Interviews, role plays, talks, conversations, and games are the types of interpersonal speaking performance.

** Extensive (monologue)*

The teacher assigns prolonged monologues in the form of oral reports, summaries, narratives, and brief speeches.

From the aforementioned theory, teachers may derive several significant teaching elements for speaking. Students must possess the vocabulary, pronunciation, and language functions in English that they will utilize. Instructors can then aid pupils in utilizing their speaking skills. Their expertise and habits are particularly useful for correctly developing the language.

2.2. ELSA Speak Application

2.2.1. General information about ELSA Speak

There is a wide range of digital platforms, software and applications functioning as a tool for language acquisition (Joy, 2017). ELSA Speak is a typical example of application (app) on mobile devices, helping to polish English learners' pronunciation. Established in 2015 by Vu Van, a Vietnamese founder, a speech scientist Xavier Anguera, and Paul Meier, a linguistic professional, in the USA, this app utilizes its proprietary artificial intelligence (AI) technology, serving as a personal pronunciation coach for the users. The

acronym ELSA stands for English Learning Speech Assistant, so the name of this app is self-defined.

This app is trusted by several prestigious organizations and institutions worldwide as they have already offered ELSA as a preferred English training solution to their employees. Some of the strategic partners of ELSA are British Council, IDP, Kyoto University, Fulbright, and Nanyang Technological University.

2.2.2. The key features of ELSA Speak

As an AI-powered English speaking coach, this app provides users with these following features:

- Tracking users' progress and achievements
- Detailed analysis of users' speaking score
- Daily personalized coaching program
- Bite-sized lessons covering 44 English language sounds on various topics

The progress of ELSA Speak's users is calculated based on five criteria: Pronunciation, fluency, intonation, word stress, and listening via six gamified activities:

- Pronunciation
- Intonation
- Word stress
- Conversation
- Video conversation
- Listening

The similarity among these activities (apart from Listening activities) is that students' pronunciation is assessed after they repeat a single word, a phrase, or a whole sentence. Such users' utterances are recorded automatically, and during the lesson, the users can replay both the samples given by ELSA

Speak and their own recording, being able to compare how they sound and pinpoint the difference between the way they pronounce and that of native speakers.

Regarding the first three types of activity, users are given topic-based vocabulary (words/phrases/sentences) in order to read aloud after listening to the model speakers. After that, their pronunciation is evaluated with detailed feedback, including the accuracy rate and the tips on how to articulate the words more accurately. As a result, the users' pronunciation would become better after following the step-by-step instruction provided on the application.

“Video conversation” is a role-play activity in which the simulations of daily conversations are designed and computerized, thereby allowing users to interact with the characters in the videos provided based on already made transcripts. Likewise, “Conversation” is two-way conversation exercises that allow users to explore how a conversation proceeds in real-life situations, enabling them to read aloud the sentences in return after receiving an utterance in the dialogue.

“Listening” activities on ELSA Speak are utilized in order to help learners differentiate the similar phonemes, which is one of the key elements to sound correct in English.

All of the aforementioned activities are classified into three levels: easy, medium, and difficult. This would be calculated based on personal progress of every user.

2.2.3. The science behind the mechanism of ELSA Speak

ELSA's AI technology is based on voice data from people speaking English with a variety of accents. This enables the program to recognize the speech patterns of its users, providing them with real-time speech recognition feedback.

It is available on both the AppStore and the Google Play store and has a variety of features to improve learners' pronunciation of words, phrases, and sentences with an American accent through exercises that ask learners to pronounce them correctly. The application can determine the speaking proficiency and score of a student. Prior research has concluded that pupils gain a great deal from using this application to learn English.

ELSA grows more intelligent every day. Their personalized English instruction technology transforms conventional language learning. Their self-evolving AI analyzes performance and behavioral data to customize the daily curriculum for each individual.

2.3. Previous studies related to using ELSA Speak to enhance speaking skills

The topic of utilizing ELSA Speak in English language teaching has gained interest and attentions of several researchers since its advent. A number of researchers affirm that this application is a pedagogical tool to help students improve their speaking competence.

One of the latest studies related to ELSA Speak is conducted by Dhivya (2023), titled “ELSA as an Education 4.0 Tool for Learning Business English Communication”. The purpose of this research is to improve Business English communication using ELSA Speak. The utilization of ELSA to improve Business English communication is the novelty of the study. This quantitative study used a quasi-experimental design and a purposive sampling technique to select participants. For this study, management students from business institutions were chosen. This investigation included the participation of 99 students. Subsequently, a questionnaire-based pre-test was administered. The collection and documentation of data. The intervention lasted four weeks and incorporated ELSA Speak. After the intervention period, an additional

questionnaire was administered as a post-test to assess any improvement. Participants' pre- and post-test data were contrasted and analyzed in SPSS using a paired sample t-test. The results demonstrated that ELSA Speak significantly improved listening skills, which is also essential for enhancing other skills, and the participants benefited from its use.

Similarly, Adhan (2021), in his paper “Elsa Speak App: Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) for Supplementing English Pronunciation Skills”, concludes that ELSA Speak can really enhance students’ pronunciation as well as incentive them to engage in learning how to pronounce English sounds effectively in the class-room context. In this study, the data were gathered by a pronunciation test and interviews with the participating students from English Department of Nahdlatul Ulama University of Yogyakarta.

Similarly, according to Samad and Ismail (2020) in their research titled “ELSA Speak Application as a Supporting Media in Enhancing Students’ Pronunciation Skill”, the effectiveness of using ELSA Speak for improving students’ pronunciation is also verified by their experimental research design. The participants of the study were students from an English study program of STKIP Muhammadiyah Enrekang in the academic year 2018-2019. Consideration was given to the fact that the sample was enrolled in a pronunciation course at the time the sample was selected. Using the recording, the pre-test and post-test were administered to collect the data. The obtained data were statistically analyzed. It indicated that the application ELSA Speak is effective in improving the pronunciation skills of the institution's first-semester students.

Another work, named “ELSA Speak - Accent Reduction (Review)” conducted by Kimberly and Idee (2019) focused more on the accent reduction effect of ELSA Speak, considering it as a great stride in the world of AI for

training individual's pronunciation. Before moving on to a critical evaluation of the free version of the app, the authors provide an overview of its basic features. Nevertheless, in this paper, it is suggested that the functions should be upgraded to include suprasegmental respects regarding pronunciation, particularly in the aspect of accent reduction.

With regard to learners' perspectives, Endang et al. (2020) reveal that most of the university students have positive feedback towards using ELSA Speak. In their paper, "Using ELSA App in Speaking Classes: Students' Voices", four classes of students enrolled in an English Education study program were polled regarding their opinions of the ELSA App. It was discovered that the majority of students agreed that the ELSA Speak App is a useful tool for enhancing their speaking ability, particularly in terms of pronunciation. Moreover, the study was conducted under the situation of the Covid-19 pandemic where ELSA Speak is just a supplementary besides other online learning platforms.

In Vietnam, the utilization of ELSA Speak to refine students' speaking skill is a new topic of concern. Do (2018) conducted a case study to investigate the effectiveness of ELSA Speak on learning English pronunciation with first year English language teaching majors at Hanoi Pedagogical University 2. The data of this research was collected both qualitatively and quantitatively from four instruments, namely questionnaire, interview, ELSA Assessment Test and Student Oral Language Observation Matrix score. The findings of this study indicate that ELSA Speak is an educational application that is useful for both upgrading students' pronunciation and boosting their confidence at the same time.

In conclusion, regarding the literature review, it can be concluded that ELSA Speak is widely utilized by educators in many nations, including

Vietnam. Numerous studies have been conducted to determine the advantages of using this application. They demonstrated that ELSA Speak can help students improve their speaking skills. However, no research has been conducted on the effectiveness of ELSA Speak in developing students' speaking skills for self-study in a provincial high school. As a result, the author of this study implemented the use of this application to improve the speaking skills of high school students in a self-study context.

2.4. Chapter summary

In this chapter, the definitions, components, and stages of teaching speaking skills have been discussed in relation to teaching and learning speaking skills. In addition, this chapter explains the concepts and component of speaking competence, as well as different types of speaking performance. In addition, a review of history of English language teaching is included in this chapter. Besides, an insightful investigation about the mechanism of ELSA Speak algorithm is also provided. Furthermore, previous studies conducted by both foreign and Vietnamese researchers are mentioned. In such particular context as self-learning, however, no research has been conducted on the effectiveness of employing ELSA Speak to improve students' speaking skills. Consequently, these previous studies serve as a foundation for the researcher's current study, which examines the effects of a variety of interactive activities designed to develop students' speaking abilities.

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

In the preceding chapter of the thesis, the author provides an overview of the principal issues and notable studies related to the research topic in order to lay the theoretical groundwork for the entire paper. This chapter presents the context of this study, which consists of the context of the school, English teachers, students, and the current situation of teaching and learning English in general and speaking skills in particular in the school, as well as the description of the material. In addition, it provides an insightful description of the research design, research methodology, including data collection methods, research instruments, data collection procedures, as well as the research participants.

3.1. Context of the study

3.1.1. An overview of the high school

The study paper is conducted in a provincial high school at the end of the first semester of the session 2022-2023. The high school is considered one of the top-ranking institutions in Ninh Binh province.

The school has made incredible attempts to improve its existing training facilities and standardized learning environment, allowing learners to benefit from the finest educational conditions for their learning in general and English practice in particular. The majority of classrooms in the school are supplied with technological devices and equipment, including computers, projectors, wireless speakers, and air conditioners.

The teachers and staff have always prioritized innovative educational methods and students' individual learning preferences, thereby enabling students to unlock their full potential.

Up until now, generations of pupils have become prosperous business owners, educators, engineers, and so on, always devoting themselves to their

homeland. Likewise, all of the school's teachers are well-trained professionals with a lengthy track record of success in the field of education. The Provincial People's Committee and the Ministry of Education and Training awarded noble titles to a number of instructors, while others received certificates of merit.

3.1.2. English language training in the school

The school offers 10 specialized classes in subjects such as math, physics, English, and so on. Specifically, English is one of the school's strongest training assets. In recent years, the school has won numerous awards at the National English Competitions for Outstanding Students. In order to attain these accomplishments, the school's instructors possess not only superior knowledge but also a tremendous passion for their profession. Additionally, the school's students are distinguished by qualities such as diligence, originality, and forbearance.

3.1.3. Participants

Participating in the research were fifteen members of a class. They are specializing in English after studying it for many years. However, a significant number of them lack confidence and are reluctant to communicate in English. As a result, they have difficulty enhancing their English language skills. Student 01, Student 02, etc. are used to protect the anonymity of study participants. The researcher was also a participant who served as a facilitator for their speaking activities during self-study with ELSA Speak at home. This does foster a consistent protocol for conducting this research.

3.2. Research design

3.2.1. Research approach

3.2.1.1. Rationale for the use of Action Research

Action research, a term coined by Lewin in the 1940s, is "a comparative research on the conditions and effects of various forms of social action," offering "a spiral step" consisting of "circles of planning, action, and fact-

finding about the outcome of the action." In other words, it is genuinely regarded as "learning by doing" (O' Brien, 1993), which means that when a group of individuals confront a problem, they take action to solve it and evaluate the success of their efforts; and if they are not pleased with the outcome, they can attempt again. In the context of education, action research is recognized as a powerful instrument for classroom and educational research because it is an instance of self-reflective investigation that teachers may employ to enhance the justification and accountability of their own methods of instruction, as well as their comprehension of these procedures and the contexts in which they occur. Therefore, action research in the context of education is a study conducted by instructors in a particular setting to enhance the standard of instruction and student achievement.

As a teacher of English, the author is acutely aware of the challenges that the pupils endure in enhancing their English speaking abilities. In contemplating an appropriate methodology for this thesis, the author determined that action research is the most effective method to develop students' speaking skills.

3.2.1.2. Model of Action Research

According to Burns (1999), each action research study is unique and therefore permits the researcher to select the most applicable dynamics. In addition, action research is a changing, fluid process, and there is no predetermined procedure for how to proceed. Consequently, action research procedures vary depending on the researcher's viewpoints.

Moreover, Kemmis and McTaggart (1988) devise a similar framework for action research. They propose a four-step spiral model consisting of planning (recognizing an issue and figuring out possible tactics), acting (implementing the tactics), observing (tracking results of the tactics), and reflecting (assessing outcomes of the tactics).

Figure 3.1. The model of action research by Kemmis & Taggart (1988, p.85)

Another structure developed by Nunan (1992) consists of seven consecutive stages for the action cycle.

Table 3.1. Steps in the action cycle (by Nunan, 1992)

Step 1	<i>Initiation</i>	An issue inspires the concept of action research.
Step 2	<i>Preliminary investigation</i>	Collecting baseline data assists in comprehending the nature of the problem.
Step 3	<i>Hypotheses</i>	After the initial data is analyzed, a hypothesis is developed.
Step 4	<i>Intervention</i>	Several strategies are developed and implemented.
Step 5	<i>Evaluation</i>	To assess the intervention, an evaluation is conducted. There may be repetitive stages.
Step 6	<i>Dissemination</i>	The research's findings are publicized. The research-derived concepts are disseminated.
Step 7	<i>Follow-up</i>	Alternative solutions to the problem are investigated perpetually.

Because of its simplicity and clarity, the researcher believed that Nunan's model would be the most suitable action cycle for the study's design among the classifications listed above.

The cycle outlined in this thesis can be illustrated as follows:

Figure 3.2. The cycle conducted in the thesis

3.2.2. Research instruments

In this study, both quantitative and qualitative data are gathered. Quantitative data are gathered by calculating students' speaking test scores. To gain insight into the current situation of the students, including the cause of the problem with their speaking abilities, qualitative data are collected. Pre- and post-speaking tests, a questionnaire, and a semi-structured interview are the instruments deployed.

3.2.2.1. Oral test

Purpose: The author administered two tests, a pre-test and a post-test, to compare the range of students' speaking ability scores before and after the use of ELSA Speak.

Structure of oral tests: The purpose of the tests is to evaluate the student's speaking capacity at the CEFR B1 level. The tests are used to gauge five aspects of speaking abilities (Harris, 1974): comprehension, grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, and fluency. On a scale ranging from 0 (low) to 2 (high), each component was rated. The highest attainable score on the Oral test is 10.

Participants: 15 10th graders in a class

Procedure: The pre-test was delivered for the participants. The test was taken before the use of ELSA Speak. It took each student about 10 - 15 minutes to finish the test. After the intervention stage, a post-test was used in order to identify and determine if the application of ELSA Speak improved student's speaking skills. Finally, the collected data were analyzed. The intervention duration was 2 months, and the researcher's role was a facilitator and supervisor.

3.2.2.2. *Questionnaire*

A questionnaire is a potent instrument for collecting information about affective aspects of teaching and learning, which include opinions, inspiration, as well as preferences, and so on from a large number of respondents in a relatively brief amount of time. Therefore, this instrument was selected for use in this research.

Purpose: The purpose of the questionnaire was to investigate the students' views regarding the use of ELSA Speak in the context of self-study at home.

Structure of the questionnaire: The questionnaire (adapted from Hoàng Thị Xuân Hoa and Nguyễn Thị Thủy Minh, 2006) had five main sections: interest/enjoyment, perceived competence, effort/importance, pressure/tension, and value/usefulness. The questionnaire contained seventeen elements. On a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly concur), each item was rated.

Participants: 15 10th graders in a class

Procedure: The survey questionnaire was delivered to the participants, which took about 15 minutes for all students to complete the questionnaire. Then, the collected data were analyzed properly by the computer software.

3.2.2.3. *Semi-structured interview*

A semi-structured interview is a qualitative research technique that employs a predetermined set of discussion-provoking questions or topics with the interviewer's freedom to investigate particular themes or additional responses. Respondents do not have to stick to a predetermined list of answers, but are allowed to argue and raise issues related to the investigation's theme. Consequently, employing semi-structured interviews provides not only an understanding of the research theme to be investigated, but also an enormous amount of latitude for the researcher and a degree of flexibility in obtaining information from interviewees. These notions serve as the justification for selecting a semi-structured interview for this study.

Purpose: The interview was conducted at the final stage of the study in order to obtain additional information for evaluating the impact of ELSA Speak on fostering students' speaking skills in a provincial high school.

Structure of semi-structured interview: This interview consisted of six open-ended inquiries concerning the impact of ELSA Speak on enhancing students' speaking skills.

Participants: According to Nielson and Marck (1994), sample sizes with as few as five or six participants can provide sufficient data for drawing conclusions. Thus, the researcher conducted interviews with five students chosen at random.

Procedure: The researcher scheduled an interview time with the participants on a Sunday afternoon. Participants' pseudonyms are used in order

to safeguard the research's ethical concerns. In case the interviewees had trouble comprehending the queries in English or disliked speaking English, and the researcher conducted interviews with five students in English. At the outset of each interview, the nature of the study was conveyed to the students in a clear, explicit, and unambiguous manner. Each interview lasted between 10 and 20 minutes.

3.2.3. Data collection procedures

This action research consisted of three distinct phases: Pre-Treatment, Treatment, and Post-Treatment. The detailed procedures proposed by Nunan were also implemented to these phases in the intervention plan as follows:

Phase 1: PRE-TREATMENT

Step 1: Initiation

The researcher determined the need of intervention to be conducted in the context of self-studying to improve participants' speaking competence.

Step 2: Preliminary investigation

By analyzing the students' pre-test scores at this high school, the researcher was able to identify obstacles that prevented students from completing speaking tasks.

Step 3: Hypothesis

It was hypothesized that using ELSA Speak can enhance students' speaking skills.

Phase 2: TREATMENT

As soon as the problem was identified, preparations were made for plan implementation, and the intervention was carried out within eight consecutive weeks.

Step 4: Intervention

Based on the results of the pre-test administered during the pre-treatment phase, the researcher determined that the speaking level of the students was

low. To address the issues, the researcher utilized ELSA Speak to enhance students' speaking competence.

ELSA Speak offers a wide range of engaging activities and useful materials for users to foster their English proficiency in general and speaking ability in particular. Each student had the personalized syllabus and learning content based on their specific strengths and weaknesses provided by the app. During the time this study was conducted, the students were required to spend at least 30 minutes per day to complete their personalized activities suggested by ELSA Speak after school or whenever they felt comfortable for self-study. Their progress and performance were recorded on the management system developed for instructor (Teacher Dashboard), which is also another in-app feature of ELSA Speak.

Tutorial videos: Users can view videos of American speakers articulating the words they are learning. The videos allow them to see the facial features of the speakers along with detailed instructions, so they can learn how to appropriately articulate the words according to the International Phonetic Alphabet.

Dictionary: Users can simply visit the Dictionary and enter any word or phrase. ELSA will search on YouTube for videos of individuals uttering the entered words. If ELSA discovers a video, a video icon will appear in the bottom right corner of the screen, allowing users to press the button to begin viewing the video.

Bite-sized lessons: Lessons in ELSA are organized by skill so that users can learn each skill independently and at their own pace. Additionally, they can acquire skills through common topics such as movies, entertainment, and business, to name a few. The purpose of this is to train users to use words/phrases commonly used by native English speakers and to assist users in developing a habit of using proper grammar and sentence structure.

Assessment test: As users begin using ELSA, they will be prompted to take an assessment test to determine their current English proficiency level based on their pronunciation strengths and weaknesses. Then, an individualized lesson plan will be created for them. Users are not required to rigorously adhere to their individualized instruction plans, but it is strongly advised that they do so.

Advanced mode: After users complete each course, a report will be generated indicating the accuracy of the user's pronunciation and how to enhance it. ELSA would provide instantaneous feedback and rapidly fix users' errors. If users desire to be evaluated on their pronunciation of the entire word or phrase, they can select the "Advanced" button at the top of the page.

Progress tracking: ELSA records the progress of its users so they can see how far they have progressed.

Personalized learning plans: ELSA continually reassesses users' English pronunciation and provides them with daily tailored training courses to accelerate their progress.

Gamified activities: These include activities focusing on Listening, Conversation, Video conversation, Word stress, Intonation, and Pronunciation of learners, in which they can either decide to learn by skill or topic of conversation.

Other features: There are some other in-app functions of ELSA Speak such as "Study set" that allows users to create their own word list, "Leaderboard" to encourage users to try harder or "IELTS Speaking Score Predictor" for students preparing for their IELTS test.

Initially, the author had to invest time in supplying her students with concrete information about speaking as well as how to become familiarized with ELSA Speak. The author urged them to follow their

personalized study plan from ELSA as closely as possible, at times regardless of vocabulary, grammar, or pronunciation accuracy.

Phase 3: POST-TREATMENT

Step 5: Evaluation

After completing the implementation of ELSA Speak with the participants, the researcher administered an oral post-test to assess the students' understanding of the intervention plan involving the use of ELSA Speak to enhance speaking skills. Then, questionnaires were distributed to the students to gather information about their attitudes towards the tool's application. Before distributing the questionnaires, the researcher provided a thorough explanation of the study and a glossary of key terms to prevent any potential misunderstandings. Five semi-structured interviews were then conducted with five students to inquire about their emotions, thoughts, and opinions regarding ELSA Speak. The purpose of the interview was to verify the results of the assessments and questionnaire used in this study.

The Dissemination and Follow-Up phases finalized the action cycle when the results were reported and alternative problem-solving decisions were made.

3.3. Data analytical framework

3.3.1. Quantitative analysis

Included in the quantitative analysis are the two assessments and questionnaires. The data gathered from the exams and questionnaires were statistically analyzed using SPSS 27, which is a statistical software suite, is utilized for analyzing quantitative data collected from the oral tests to generate descriptive statistics. Descriptive statistics provide a straightforward overview of data, permitting the researcher to obtain a better understanding of the data set as a whole. In the present study, descriptive statistics of the overall development in speaking ability and attitudes toward the implementation of ELSA Speak were computed. Mean values for the entire group were computed.

The following are the steps that this study involved:

- Specify the goals and research questions.
- Create the research and gather information.
- Information Processing
- Analysis of Data: SPSS 27 was the statistical program used for this phase.
- Interpretation of Results: Following analysis, the researcher provided an interpretation of the findings in relation to the study questions.
- Presenting the Results: To summarize the replies from the participants, the findings were shown as text, tables, and graphs. Writing an explanation of the results, the statistical procedures followed, and the interpretation of the data were all required.

3.3.2. Qualitative analysis

The qualitative analysis is the transcription of the interview. The interview data were categorized, synthesized, and analyzed to determine the impact of ELSA Speak on promoting student speaking competence.

Before the researcher transcribed the MP3 recordings of individual interviews, students' responses were recorded. Each recording was approximately 10 to 15 minutes long. Then, the transcripts were analyzed based on the themes that emerged in relation to the students' use of ELSA Speak, their motivation and positive attitude toward this application, and their progress in speaking skills. The researcher then analyzed the data to determine whether the implementation of ELSA Speak aided in the improvement of students' speaking skills. The data analysis and findings were then described in detail in Chapter 4. Finally, the discussions and recommendations were presented in the following chapters.

To be more specific, the steps involved are illustrated as follows:

- A pre-arranged list of questions will be used to guide student interviews.

- The interviews are going to be verbatim transcribed from audio recordings.

- Thematic analysis will be used to examine the qualitative data. In order to identify themes and recurrent ideas, the interview transcripts will be read again and again.

- Data segments will be given codes, which will then be categorized into more general topics.

- Themes will be dissected and explained in more detail.

With reference to qualitative data from the questionnaire and semi-structure interview, a coding system for content analysis is developed as below with some examples from students' responses:

Table 3.2. Coding system for discourse analysis

Raw data	Sub-theme	Theme
<i>Student 8: "I am too embarrassed and anxious to speak in English, so I always remain silent."</i>	<i>Negative feeling</i>	<i>Pre-treatment</i>
	<i>Low engagement</i>	
<i>Student 7: "Thanks to ELSA Speak, I'm growing more comfortable communicating in English, and this app has helped me a lot with my pronunciation, intonation, and all sorts of other elements."</i>	<i>Positive feeling</i>	<i>Post-treatment</i>
	<i>High engagement</i>	

As can be seen from the table, the participants embodied their negative feeling and low engagement before the implementation of ELSA Speak. This is illustrated by "embarrassed", "anxious", and so on. By contrast, after the application of ELSA Speak, they felt more "comfortable", indicating their higher level of engagement in English conversations.

CHAPTER 4: FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter describes the results from the data analysis phase. The purpose of this study was to determine whether ELSA Speak can enhance the speaking skills of students at a provincial high school and to obtain their opinions regarding the use of ELSA Speak in a self-studying context. The oral tests, questionnaires, and semi-structured interview gathered data. The results of the research questions are subsequently provided and analyzed followed by a discussion referencing previous research.

* Analysis of students' pre-test results:

On the basis of the results of the pre-test, the students' speaking ability was evaluated.

Table 4.1. The pre-test scores of 15 students in speaking skills

Student No.	C	G	V	P	F	Score
Score	/2	/2	/2	/2	/2	10
Student 1	1	1	1	1.5	1.5	6
Student 2	1.5	0.5	1	1	1	5
Student 3	1	1.5	1.5	0.5	1	5.5
Student 4	1	0.5	1.5	1.5	0.5	5
Student 5	1	1.5	1	0.5	1	5
Student 6	1.5	1	0.5	0.5	1	4.5
Student 7	1.5	1.5	1	1	1	6
Student 8	1	1	1	0.5	1	4.5
Student 9	1.5	1	1.5	0.5	0.5	5
Student 10	1	1.5	1.5	1.5	1	6.5
Student 11	1.5	2	1	0.5	0.5	5.5

Student 12	1.5	0.5	1	0.5	0.5	4
Student 13	2	1	1.5	1.5	1	7
Student 14	1.5	1	1	1	1	5.5
Student 15	1	1.5	1	0.5	1	5
Average	1.30	1.13	1.13	0.87	0.90	5.33

Note: C = Comprehension, G = Grammar, V = Vocabulary, P = Pronunciation, F = Fluency.

As can be seen from Table 4.1, the overall mean score of the students in speaking was 5.33/10, indicating that there was still room for their improvement in speaking proficiency. Also, it is evident that the students had their highest performance in comprehension with the score of 1.3/2. This figure indicates that they could understand the key information and decipher the meaning of new words. In contrast, pronunciation and fluency were the two aspects in which students scored lowest, with 0.87 and 0.9 respectively. To be more specific, the students got difficulties pronouncing words, which hindered their conveyed messages and fluency as well. Besides, the students' limited vocabulary and grammatical ranges were also elements that prevented them from achieving higher scores in the pre-test. In general, the results demonstrated that the students had some weaknesses in speaking, regarding comprehension, pronunciation, fluency, grammar, and vocabulary respects.

4.1. Improvement of the students' speaking skills after the intervention

The researcher compared pre-and post-test scores to determine how ELSA Speak can enhance students' speaking abilities. In addition, a semi-structured interview was investigated to verify the result.

4.1.1. Oral tests

Table 4.2. The post-test scores of 15 students in speaking skills

Student No.	C	G	V	P	F	Score
Score	<i>/2</i>	<i>/2</i>	<i>/2</i>	<i>/2</i>	<i>/2</i>	10
Student 1	1.5	1	1	1.5	1.5	6.5
Student 2	1	1	1	1.5	1	5.5
Student 3	1	1.5	1.5	0.5	1.5	6
Student 4	1.5	0.5	1.5	1.5	1	6
Student 5	1.5	1.5	1	1	1.5	6.5
Student 6	1.5	1	1	1	1	5.5
Student 7	2	1.5	1	1.5	1.5	7.5
Student 8	1	1	1	1	1	5
Student 9	2	1	1.5	1	0.5	6
Student 10	2	1.5	1.5	1.5	1	7.5
Student 11	1.5	2	1	1	0.5	6
Student 12	1.5	0.5	1	1	1	5
Student 13	2	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	8
Student 14	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	7.5
Student 15	2	1.5	1.5	1	1.5	7.5
Average	1.57	1.23	1.23	1.20	1.17	6.40

Note: C = Comprehension, G = Grammar, V = Vocabulary, P = Pronunciation, F = Fluency

According to Table 4.2, students' speaking scores overall averaged 6.4/10, which shows that they performed at a respectable level across the board. According to the mean score of 1.57/2.0, comprehension was the area in which students scored the highest. It reveals that students were able to understand and process the key information necessary to ascertain the meaning of words, and

they also readily recognized and placed the words in the appropriate category. However, pronunciation and fluency received the lowest mean score, 1.2/2 and 1.17/2 respectively. Yet, when compared to the mean score of 0.87 and 0.9 from the pre-test, the students have demonstrated significant improvement in these areas. It is also notable that the component vocabulary observes a mean of 1.23. It demonstrates that the vocabulary of the pupils has considerably improved. Students are able to communicate clearly and correctly use grammar and vocabulary better. Nonetheless, individuals found it challenging to articulate their thoughts in a clear and logical manner while speaking. Also, the results reveal that pupils' speaking skills had significantly improved. They are able to convey their ideas using the new vocabulary and more complex sentence structures. Therefore, the favorable influences of ELSA Speak on students' speaking competence have been proved. In general, pronunciation and fluency are the areas in which students show their most striking progress while grammar and vocabulary are the ones in which students' performance is improved least.

Table 4.3. Descriptive statistics of the post-test scores

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
C	15.00	1.00	2.00	1.57	0.36
G	15.00	0.50	2.00	1.23	0.40
V	15.00	1.00	1.50	1.23	0.25
P	15.00	0.50	1.50	1.20	0.31
F	15.00	0.50	1.50	1.17	0.35
Score	15.00	5.00	8.00	6.40	0.95
Valid N (listwise)	15.00				

*** Comparison of test results**

Table 4.4. T-test paired sample statistics

	Paired Differences					
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Pre-test	5.333	0.794	0.205	1.623	14	0.000007
Post-test	6.400	0.986	0.255	3.740	14	0.002

Looking at the Table 4.4., the *sig.* value of equal variances assumed was $\text{sig. (2-tailed)} < \alpha = 0.05$. This indicates that there was a significant difference between the mean scores of students on the two tests. The implementation of ELSA Speak to the teaching of speaking skills resulted in greater improvement in speaking skills on the post-test compared to the pre-test. The following table illustrates the distinction between the pre-test and post-test results.

Table 4.5. Comparing the pre-test and post-test results

Component	Pre-test	Post-test
<i>Comprehension</i>	1.3	1.57
<i>Grammar</i>	1.13	1.23
<i>Vocabulary</i>	1.13	1.23
<i>Pronunciation</i>	0.87	1.2
<i>Fluency</i>	0.9	1.17
<i>Mean</i>	5.33	6.4

The comparison between the pre-test and post-test is presented in Table 4.5. The findings revealed a significant shift in the test results. It demonstrates that the implementation of ELSA Speak resulted in a substantial change in students' knowledge, which was reflected in the development of students' speaking abilities. Consequently, the post-test demonstrated a positive change

in student performance. In particular, the mean score for pronunciation increased from 0.87/2.0 to 1.2/2.0. The average score for fluency increased from 0.9/2.0 to 1.17/2.0. Regarding vocabulary, the mean score has risen from 1.13/2.0 to 1.23/2.0, representing an improvement. Following the implementation of ELSA Speak, participants demonstrated improved grammatical proficiency. This is evidenced by the change from 1.13/2.0 to 1.23/2.0 in the mean score. The mean of the final component changes from 1.3/2.0 to 1.57/2.0. As a result, the overall mean score increased significantly from 5.33/10 to 6.4/10. Considering the difference between the pre- and post-test mean scores, the results indicated accomplishment. It demonstrates that the use of ELSA Speak has led to a significant development in students' speaking abilities.

4.1.2. Semi-structured interview

For the purpose of gathering more detailed data, a semi-structured interview was conducted with three students (ST7, ST14, and ST15) who made the most substantial advancement in the selected class during the period of intervention and two students (ST8 and ST11) who made only slight progress. The questions and responses were in English.

When asked about the students' willingness to participate in lessons prior to the intervention, all five participants reported that they rarely volunteered to use ELSA Speak with standard assignments prior to the intervention. When two of them confessed that they had never been willing to speak. Two students disclosed that they rarely participated in class discussions in English. Only student 4 indicated that he occasionally initiated English conversation. Student 8 stated, "I am too embarrassed and anxious to speak in English, so I always remain silent." I don't attempt to speak in English". Student 11 added, "I find it hard to ignite a conversation in this foreign language."

When asked about students' active role in English conversations prior to the intervention, the majority of respondents indicated that they rarely spoke prior to the implementation of the new technique. Three students reported that they occasionally spoke in class, but only said one or two brief sentences. They also provided explanations, such as "I have no idea about where to start, so I fail to speak English" (student 8). Or, "when my instructor requests me to say something, I participate minimally." Two additional students reported that they had barely participated in English conversation.

In brief, based on the responses to the first two questions, it can be concluded that prior to the intervention in which ELSA Speak were implemented, neither the students who volunteered to speak nor those who participated in speaking did so in day-to-day situations.

When asked if their speaking skills had improved after the implementation of the intervention plan, each student responded affirmatively. They were extremely content with the use of ELSA Speak activities. Student 14 stated, "This application allows me to practice and rectify my pronunciation. Thus, it enables me to expand my vocabulary and improve my fluency. The students disclosed that ELSA Speak helped them become more interested in public speaking, to speak for longer periods of time, and to express their ideas with greater fluency. Additionally, ELSA Speak enabled them to acquire accurate speech. They assisted them in reviewing grammatical structures and vocabulary in order to identify errors in sentences using the acquired knowledge. For example, student 9 remarked, "Many real-life scenarios are incorporated into the lessons, which are essential to our everyday conversations." In addition, student 7 said, "Thanks to ELSA Speak, I'm growing more comfortable communicating in English, and this app has helped me a lot with my pronunciation, intonation, and all sorts of other elements." In

particular, another responded wittily that "ELSA Speak encourages us to take part in speaking during lessons."

4.2. Students' opinions towards the application of ELSA Speak in their learning of English speaking skills

To examine students' attitudes toward the implementation of ELSA Speak, the researcher chose to adapt Hoàng Thị Xuân Hoa and Nguyễn Thị Thủy Minh's (2006) self-questionnaire. Five previously selected students participated in a semi-structured interview to verify the results of the questionnaire. Questionnaire data were analyzed regarding five sections: Interest/enjoyment, Perceived competence, Effort/importance, Pressure/tension and Value/usefulness.

4.2.1. Questionnaire

4.2.1.1. Student's interest/enjoyment

Table 4.6. The interest/enjoyment of students

Item No.	Statement	No. of students				
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Unsure	Agree	Strongly agree
1	Activities on ELSA Speak are engaging.	1 (7%)	1 (7%)	3 (20%)	7 (46%)	3 (20%)
2	I am excited about using ELSA Speak.	1 (7%)	1 (7%)	5 (30%)	6 (40%)	2 (13%)
3	I preferred learning on ELSA Speak.	2 (14%)	1 (7%)	3 (20%)	5 (30%)	4 (26%)

From the data provided in the table, it is evident that "agree" and "strongly agree" garner the highest percentages, with responses ranging from

53% to 66%. The number of students selecting "disagree" and "strongly disagree" was significantly lower. When asked if they were eager to use ELSA Speak for self-study, up to 63% of the students concurred. On the third item, up to the majority of respondents also indicated that they preferred learning on this new platform.

Although most of the participants demonstrate their ardent excitement about learning speaking through ELSA Speak, a small number of the participants opt for the options "unsure", "disagree", or "strongly disagree". In particular, for the first item, the percentage of respondents marking "unsure" constitutes a fifth of the total responses. 6% of those surveyed did not know if they felt enthusiastic about learning with ELSA Speak, and the final item witnessed 14%, 7%, and 20% for the options of "unsure", "disagree", and "strongly disagree" correspondingly.

To conclude, it can be observed that the majority of respondents reached the agreement that they preferred using ELSA Speak. Furthermore, students demonstrated their desire for learning ELSA Speak in general.

4.2.1.2. Students' perceived competence

This set of items was designed to investigate the participants' perceived competence through using ELSA Speak. The specific data of the survey were presented in Table 4.6.

Table 4.7. The perceived competence of students

Item No.	Statement	No. of students				
		Strong disagree	Disagree	Unsure	Agree	Strongly agree
4	I find it easier to speak with others thanks to ELSA Speak.	1 (7%)	1 (7%)	2 (14%)	6 (40%)	5 (32%)
5	I could speak more fluently thanks to ELSA Speak.	1 (7%)	1 (7%)	2 (14%)	7 (46%)	4 (26%)
6	I'm satisfied with my performance at these activities.	3 (20%)	3 (20%)	3 (20%)	3 (20%)	3 (20%)
7	Thanks to ELSA Speak, I was more confident in speaking in English.	1 (7%)	1 (7%)	4 (26%)	6 (40%)	3 (20%)

According to the table, approximately 70% of the respondents agreed that they found it simpler to communicate with others thanks to ELSA Speak, and over three-quarters of them had approval that they could speak English more fluently thanks to ELSA Speak. Up to 60% of respondents also expressed satisfaction with their performance while using this application. Moreover, the proportion of informants who selected options “(strongly) agree” when they were asked if ELSA Speak helps them feel more confident in speaking English constituted 60% of the total.

Despite the high recognition about the advantages of ELSA Speak, the data from Table 4.7 also presents some unfavorable results. For the item 4, 14% of the participants disagreed, while the same minority felt unsure. In addition, the majority of the students felt dissatisfied with their performance on ELSA Speak.

Generally, the table above indicate a large percentage of informants stating that ELSA Speak brought about a number of merits because they felt easier to speak with others and satisfied with their performance. Moreover, they could speak more fluently and showed their confidence in speaking English.

4.2.1.3. Students' effort/importance and pressure/tension

Table 4.8. The effort/importance and pressure/tension of students

Item No.	Statement	No. of students				
		Strong disagree	Disagree	Unsure	Agree	Strongly agree
8	I put a lot of effort into learning on ELSA Speak.	2 (14%)	3 (20%)	3 (20%)	7 (46%)	0 (0%)
9	I prepared a lot for the activities on ELSA Speak.	3 (20%)	4 (26%)	4 (26%)	2 (14%)	2 (14%)
10	I felt comfortable while working on ELSA Speak.	1 (7%)	1 (7%)	3 (20%)	6 (40%)	4 (26%)
11	I was always active to use ELSA Speak instead of being asked by anyone.	2 (14%)	2 (14%)	4 (26%)	4 (26%)	3 (20%)

According to the chart, the percentage of informants who chose "(strongly) agree" when asked if they put a lot of effort into ELSA Speak made up approximately a half of the total. Furthermore, a relatively the same proportion of participants said that they had done a lot of preparation for these tasks, and nearly 70% of them agreed that they felt comfortable when working on these activities. Finally, around two thirds of students stated that they were always active to use ELSA Speak rather than being reminded. However, when it comes to item 9, 26% of respondents declared "unsure" and 20% stated their (strong) disapproval, but the percentages for the same possibilities in item 10 accounted for 8% and 16% of the total. Furthermore, only a small minority claimed that they did not feel comfortable while working on ELSA Speak. For item 11, the majority of the students revealed that they were not really active in using ELSA Speak without anyone's reminder.

4.2.1.4. Students' evaluation for value/usefulness of interactive activities

As being asked for evaluation for value/ usefulness of interactive activities, total responses of the students were reported in Table 4.8 below.

Table 4.9. The value/usefulness of interactive activities

Item No.	Statement	No. of students				
		Strong disagree	Disagree	Unsure	Agree	Strongly agree
12	ELSA Speak created the real need for me to communicate.	1 (7%)	1 (7%)	5 (30%)	4 (28%)	4 (28%)
13	ELSA Speak helped me to develop my speaking ability.	0 (0%)	1 (7%)	2 (14%)	7 (49%)	5 (30%)
14	ELSA Speak helped me to react towards speaking situations more quickly.	1 (7%)	1 (7%)	3 (20%)	5 (33%)	5 (33%)
15	ELSA Speak offered me a chance to talk in English for a long time.	1 (7%)	1 (7%)	2 (14%)	5 (30%)	6 (42%)
16	ELSA Speak helped me to practice what I have learnt in real conversations.	1 (7%)	1 (7%)	3 (20%)	7 (46%)	3 (20%)

As can be seen from the table, the large majority of students agreed that ELSA Speak helps creating the real need for them to communicate in English. Besides, regarding the item 13, only a marginal percentage of the respondents (7%) disagreed that ELSA Speak helped them to develop their speaking ability. Well under 90% of the students thought that ELSA Speak offered them a chance to talk in English for a long time, and just one fifth of them felt this application helped users to practice what they have learned in real conversations.

4.2.2. Semi-structured interview

During the interviews, the researcher devised a series of questions to ask the selected students in order to further explain and improve the statistical findings. The questions were broad enough to allow respondents to freely express their thoughts, feelings, or views. Depending on the circumstances, the author might utilize these additional probing questions during the interviews. Among the responders, five of the aforementioned pupils were chosen for a semi-structured interview. The answers are discussed further below.

When asked if they thought interactive activities on ELSA Speak were entertaining, all students had a favorable attitude toward adopting this application in their learning. "ELSA Speak makes me feel more prepared to speak as I have learned a lot of new words with accurate pronunciation," remarked student 14. Furthermore, student 15 stated, "ELSA Speak is particularly fascinating since it provides an enjoyable learning environment for us to practice." In general, all of the respondents stated that they liked studying English on ELSA Speak.

Ultimately, all students expressed an interest in improving their English speaking abilities through interactive activities on ELSA Speak since these activities were useful in a variety of ways. Most students frequently felt inspired because they found this application to be both fascinating and beneficial.

4.3. Discussion on the improvement of the students' speaking skills after the intervention

The researcher attempted to employ various scaffolding tactics while introducing ELSA Speak with the intention of assisting students in improving their speaking abilities. The outcomes of the study clearly showed that the results were good. Students' English speaking abilities improved significantly.

This significant shift can be seen in the increase in mean scores from the pre-test of 5.33/10 to the post-test mean score of 6.4/10, indicating that students' speaking abilities were enhanced through the utilization of ELSA Speak.

Fluency, pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, and comprehension were the components used to assess speaking abilities. These factors enabled the teacher to determine the pupils' degree of speaking ability. Students had intonation and pronunciation issues while pronouncing words. Similarly, participants in fluency reported problems in expressing their views in an understandable and logical manner. In grammar, they struggled to generate grammatically acceptable sentences and to employ these forms correctly as the situation demanded. Finally, in comprehension, students were unable to process and recognize the important information required to express themselves. As a result, the researcher applied several scaffolding tactics to enhance the problems. For example, the author employed clues, such as suggested open-ended questions or thinking aloud tactics, to assist students with their learning with ELSA Speak. Students were offered opportunities to participate in the activities and to express their thoughts in English. During the intervention, special care was taken to ensure that pupils participated in the activities. As a consequence, students' English speaking abilities improved significantly, as evidenced by post-test results following the adoption of interactive activities. Students were able to communicate clearly and confidently by expressing

themselves, identifying grammatical structures, accurately pronouncing words, and employing new vocabulary.

The student interviews were also centered on this topic in order to clarify and augment the statistical data. According to the data gathered, the majority of the participants spoke English at an average level. Despite this, in terms of improving students' speaking skills, it can be concluded that student participation improved significantly, with the majority of students claiming they spoke more frequently and for longer periods of time, which is consistent with the results of the pre-test and post-test.

In brief, data were collected and properly analyzed in order to provide adequate responses to the research objectives of this thesis. It is possible to conclude that the use of ELSA Speak enhanced the speaking abilities of 10th graders at this high school.

4.4. Discussion on the students' opinions towards the application of ELSA Speak in their learning of English speaking skills

4.4.1. Discussion from the questionnaire

In response to the students' questionnaires on their interest in learning to speak on ELSA Speak, it was clear that the majority of students were eager to participate in this application. In terms of students' perceived competence, a large percentage of participants stated that speaking with others in English was simpler for them. In terms of fluency, the results suggested that most students thought that ELSA Speak would help them speak more fluently. The majority of students also expressed satisfaction with their performance in these activities and increased confidence in speaking English. However, several pupils were dissatisfied with their performance in interactive activities on ELSA Speak. As a result, this issue must be addressed and rectified.

The topic of students' effort/importance and pressure/tension was also highlighted in this thesis. A high proportion of students believed that they put in a lot of work and prepared extensively for these tasks. The students also stated that they felt at ease when participating in these activities. Furthermore, rather than being asked by the teacher, several students stated that they were always engaged in participating in interactive activities.

In terms of students' perceptions of the value/utility of interactive activities, the majority of informants stated that these activities produced a genuine desire for them to communicate. Furthermore, these activities aided in the development of their public speaking skills.

These exercises encouraged students to react more rapidly to speaking situations, gave them the opportunity to communicate in English for an extended period of time, and allowed them to apply what they had learned in real discussions. However, a tiny minority of respondents were dubious about the benefits of ELSA Speak in English speaking conversations. They were skeptical that these activities would create a genuine desire for them to communicate. They were also unclear whether these activities would provide them with enough opportunities to converse in English for an extended period of time. Many students, in particular, remained suspicious, even refusing to accept that these activities helped them respond to speaking situations more rapidly. With all of the previously listed factors, the deficiencies should be addressed as quickly as possible.

Taking into account the findings of previous research, ELSA Speak may encourage pupils to use English during the teaching and learning process. As a consequence of the research, the author recommended that a teacher use the application for facilitating student's speaking competence. A teacher should also adapt the activities so that pupils are not bored, intimidated, or unmotivated

to participate in class discussions. It is also advised that teachers employ diverse activities as an alternate method of English teaching learning, particularly in the area of speaking abilities.

4.4.2. Discussion from semi-structured interview with students

As mentioned before, to get in-depth data for the study, five students were asked to answer questions related to learning English speaking skills through interactive activities.

The interview with the students was focused on in this thesis to clarify and supplement the statistical results. The collected information showed that most of the participants were at average English speaking level. Despite of that, they still enjoyed learning English speaking lessons through interactive activities because these activities brought about many benefits such as: helping them feel more confident to speak English and learn many new words with correct pronunciation, creating relaxing learning environment for students to take part in, and providing good chances for students to expose confidently.

As being asked whether the students felt motivated to take part in interactive activities, most of them showed positive feelings. They agreed that interactive activities could enhance their motivation in speaking although each of them gave their own reasons. For example, student 9 replied: “I am excited at these speaking lessons and I feel free to talk in English”. Student 23 gave another reason that is “we are able to communicate more fluently and smoothly thanks to interactive activities in these lessons”. Moreover, student 4 said that “I look forward to the lessons in which I have a chance to share my knowledge to my classmates”. Even student 8 claimed that the lessons applied interactive activities create comfortable atmosphere in classroom which makes me more confident and interested in speaking”.

Majority of students found the speaking lessons more exciting and livelier. They had good chances to engage themselves in speaking activities at class and to freely express their ideas. This could be considered as an extremely good base for students to develop their brainpower and their activeness and confidence. More importantly, plenty of students understood the role of interactive activities in facilitating their speaking learning process. Consequently, students felt more confident and less anxious about their speaking ability. Besides, most of students showed their eagerness in participating in the groups and expressing themselves. Through interactive activities, they had the good chance to learn from the better ones and in contrast, they could share what they knew for the others. This made the learning process become more meaningful and educational. Accordingly, students recognized that interactive activities stimulated a cooperative learning among them and helped them improve their speaking ability.

In short, using interactive activities was a worth application on teaching and learning speaking skills. It helps students improve their speaking skills performance as well as change their attitude towards the speaking process positively.

Taking into account the results of the studies carried out in this regard, the findings of this study are in line with findings by some scholars, e.g. Jackson Steven Padilla's (2019) who claimed that the students' reading comprehension improved remarkably. However, this study also clarified that most students highly appreciated the use of interactive activities in learning speaking skills. In line with above findings, Herlita Susanti (2011) found out that the students were satisfied with their improvement and they also enjoyed their speaking activities.

To summarize, this chapter presented data on students' speaking performance and attitudes about the use of ELSA Speak. The results reveal that

following the intervention of ELSA Speak in speaking sessions, the students' speaking abilities improved significantly and they exhibited favorable views. Learning is greatly enhanced when the classroom climate is cooperative and encouraging. The author was able to progressively advance the learning process by allowing students to work with ELSA Speak and providing the necessary supervision. Scaffolding was a vital component in the development of students' speaking abilities. Prior to the intervention, the majority of the participants' speaking abilities were low to average. It was greatly improved with the aid of interactive exercises and the teacher. The teacher's help was gradually lessened, and they were able to speak English more fluently and confidently. This might be regarded as useful evidence in answering the research questions outlined in Chapter 1.

CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSION

5.1. Recapitulation

The goal of this study, as stated in the introduction, is to identify the improvement of second-year students' speaking skills after the implementation of ELSA Speak, as well as to examine the students' attitudes toward the use of the application in their learning of English speaking skills. To accomplish the aforementioned goal, data collected through exams, questionnaires, and semi-structured interviews was extensively evaluated and explained.

ELSA Speak has a favorable influence on students' speaking abilities in the context of the study. It was proved as a fantastic and beneficial strategy for improving pupils' speaking abilities. Interactive activities, in particular, have the potential to not only make the learning process more engaging, but also to promote students' development of speaking abilities. It increases student enthusiasm, facilitates collaborative effort, stimulates creativity, and recycles information. Finally, ELSA Speak is recognized as a pedagogical method for improving speaking abilities.

There was an obvious effectiveness in students' speaking skills under the treatment of ELSA Speak. Students' speaking ability improved after eight weeks of employing this strategy in teaching and mastering speaking abilities. This might be demonstrated by the individuals' post-test mean. The mean of the post-test findings revealed a significant statistical difference when compared to the one of the pre-test. Based on this, it is possible to infer that adopting interactive activities to increase students' speaking skills is a successful strategy.

The majority of pupils agreed that ELSA Speak is beneficial. Students' responses indicated that they agreed with the impacts of ELSA Speak on their speaking abilities. They discovered that the interactive exercises were

engaging, intelligible, and beneficial to their learning. Then, through interactive activities, students investigated a variety of its advantages. Many students answered that these activities produced a genuine desire for them to communicate. Furthermore, these activities assisted them in developing their speaking skills, reacting more rapidly to speaking situations, and providing them with opportunities to communicate in English for extended periods of time. Furthermore, interactive exercises allowed students to practice what they had learned in real-life dialogues. Furthermore, pupils appeared to be more involved in the class and more interested in the topic. They were aware of the advantages that ELSA Speak may provide. The students thought that it may help them enhance their speaking abilities while also creating a relaxed setting in which they could practice speaking in class.

The author was able to gradually develop the process of learning by allowing students to use ELSA Speak and offering the direction they needed to complete the assignments.

5.2. Implications

Based on the results of the study, a number of theoretical and practical concerns regarding the implementation of teacher-led interactive activities on ELSA Speak at a high school that primarily places additional expectations on instructors arise.

Teachers should learn to identify effective strategies to teach speaking skills. To foster students' interest in and engagement in public speaking lessons, teachers should consider the advantages of employing interactive activities to teach speaking. Teachers should organize their lessons based on the requirements of their students and choose the most appropriate activities that will allow learners to overcome their limits and help them reach the class goals.

It is also important to highlight that in order to stimulate students to speak English when engaging in interactive activities, the instructor should consider

elements such as creating a welcoming classroom environment and supporting cooperative learning. A welcoming classroom setting will be more appealing to children, allowing them to build cognitive skills while studying in an enjoyable way.

5.3. Limitations of the study

Despite the fact that all of the research questions have been answered and the study's objectives have been met, the study has the following main limitations.

To begin, the study was done with a small group of students (15 in all) in a high school. This may make it difficult for the researcher to collect enough data and gain an overall picture of the data under study. As a result, future study on this issue should include a greater number of people.

Second, owing to time constraints, the last phase of follow-up, in which the researcher examines other solutions to the problem, is missing. As a result, additional researchers should carry out all phases, including the last one, to explore for new approaches to boost students' motivation and engagement in speaking.

Finally, if the researcher could have used additional study tools, the validity of the findings and the dependability of the implications would have been increased.

5.4. Suggestions for further study

Using ELSA Speak to develop speaking abilities is still a large field of research. Further study might provide a more comprehensive understanding of the usage of other applications like ELSA Speak and their combination to assist students enhance their speaking ability in general and their English level in particular.

Furthermore, it is strongly advised that additional studies be undertaken with a greater number of participants over a longer period of time, as well as the inclusion of one more research instrument.

5.5. Concluding remark

This study provided more insight on the aspects of using ELSA Speak and used a combination of oral exams, questionnaires, and interviews to address research questions in self-study setting. Furthermore, this study has supplied crucial proof to the hypothesis that ELSA Speak could improve students' speaking skills. The author was able to systematically improve the process of learning by allowing students to work with ELSA Speak and providing the necessary supervision. Prior to the intervention, the majority of the participants' speaking abilities were low to average. It was greatly improved with the assistance of ELSA Speak and the author.

Nonetheless, it is evident that the author encountered several challenges when implementing the application and conducting the research. Besides, the students' motivation had been boosted, and they were eager to speak English in class. Students were considerably more secure in presenting their opinions after being terrified of speaking English in front of others. Their fluency, vocabulary, and pronunciation appeared to have much improved. This might be regarded important evidence in order to answer the thesis's research questions.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1:

SAMPLE TEST

Skill: SPEAKING

Limited time: 10 - 15 minutes

Full name

Date of birth Place of birth

Date of test

PART I (4 points): We'd like you to introduce yourself and your family. You have got 2 – 3 minutes for this part.

PART II: Topic (10 points): You have got 5 minutes for this part.

Talk about your favorite book

You should say:

- Do you like reading books? Why?
- How often do you read book?
- What is the most popular type of book in your country?

PART III: (6 points) Be ready to answer the questions related to the topic in Part II. The examiners will give you 5 questions for each topic. You have got 3–5 minutes for this part.

APPENDIX 2:

QUESTIONNAIRE

(Adapted from Hoàng Thị Xuân Hoa & Nguyễn Thị Thủy Minh, 2006)

Dear students,

I am conducting my MA research regarding the use of ELSA Speak to improve speaking competence, and I need your assistance in completing the questionnaire below. This gives me insight into the usage of ELSA Speak, and the findings of this questionnaire can assist to create more effective approaches in the future. Because this is not a test, there are no "right" or "wrong" answers, and I would appreciate it if you answered ALL of the questions honestly and properly. Your personal information will be kept completely confidential. You are NOT required to sign your name in the paperwork. Please respond to the following surveys by marking the number (1, 2, 3, 4, or 5) that appears to be most relevant to you.

Thank you for your cooperation!

1. Strongly disagree 2. Disagree 3. Unsure 4. Agree 5. Strongly agree

Category		Statement	1	2	3	4	5
1	Interest/ enjoyment	ELSA Speak were very interesting.					
		I am excited about using ELSA Speak.					
		I preferred learning on ELSA Speak.					
2	Perceived competence	I find it easier to speak with others thanks to ELSA Speak.					
		I could speak more fluently thanks to ELSA Speak.					
		I'm satisfied with my performance at the activities on ELSA Speak.					
		Thanks to ELSA Speak, I was more confident in speaking in English.					
3	Effort/ importance	I put a lot of effort into learning on ELSA Speak.					
		I prepared a lot for the activities on ELSA Speak.					

Category		Statement	1	2	3	4	5
4	Pressure/ tension	I felt comfortable while working on ELSA Speak.					
		I was always active to use ELSA Speak instead of being asked by anyone.					
5	Value/ usefulness	ELSA Speak created the real need for me to communicate.					
		ELSA Speak helped me to develop my speaking ability.					
		ELSA Speak helped me to react towards speaking situations more quickly.					
		ELSA Speak offered me a chance to talk in English for a long time.					
		ELSA Speak helped me to practice what I have learnt in real conversations.					

APPENDIX 3:

SEMI – STRUCTURED INTERVIEW

The purpose of this interview is to support my research on "*The influences of ELSA Speak on English speaking competence of 10th graders in a senior high school*".

Your help in responding is greatly appreciated. You can rest assured that this interview is solely for research purposes and that you will not be identified in any data analysis. I highly appreciate your cooperation.

Please answer these questions.

1. Before the implementation of ELSA Speak, are you active to join in speaking activities or only start speaking when being asked?
2. Before the implementation, do you often participate in speaking activities in class?
3. Do your speaking skills improve after the using ELSA Speak? If yes, can you tell me the improvement specifically?
4. Do you think the lessons and content on ELSA Speak are interesting?
5. Are you interested in using ELSA Speak? Why? Why not?

APPENDIX 4:

SEMI – STRUCTURED INTERVIEW SAMPLE

1. Before the implementation of ELSA Speak, are you active to join in speaking activities or only start speaking when being asked?

ST8: Because I constantly feel too overwhelmed with confusion and anxiety to speak in front of the class, I always remain silent. I hardly have the courage to offer to talk first.

2. Before the implementation, do you often participate in speaking activities in class?

ST8: Speaking is not something I often take part in. Since I am unable to articulate my thoughts well, my command of the English language is poor.

3. Do you think interactive activities in ELSA Speak are interesting?

ST8: Yes, they are. But maybe I didn't have much time to practice.

4. Are you interested in using ELSA Speak? Why? Why not?

ST8: Yes, I am. Because the interactive activities on ELSA Speak provide a pleasant environment for me, which makes me more confident and interested in speaking, I feel more encouraged to speak English. ELSA Speak has made me more interested in speaking.

APPENDIX 5:

SPEAKING ASSESSMENT FORM

Full name:

Date:

Criteria	Comment	Score
Comprehension		
Grammar		
Vocabulary		
Pronunciation		
Fluency		
Overall		